

D5.3 Interim Report on Data Infrastructure update and extension

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1 Executive Summary

The deliverable reports work done in Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.7 during the first 36 months of the project, providing an update to D5.2, and assessing what has been accomplished to date and planning the related activities for the final period, i.e. months 37-48. Work done under Task 5.6 has previously been reported in D5.1. Related activity has been reported in D4.1 and D4.2.

ARIADNEplus seeks to update and extend the research data infrastructure delivered within the preceding ARIADNE project (2013-17). It extends ARIADNE in several dimensions:

1. Wider geographical coverage with new partners.
2. Wider disciplinary coverage with a greater emphasis on the sub-domains of palaeo-anthropology, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology, material sciences, dating methods, and on the archaeology of standing structures.
3. The time span considered.
4. The depth of database integration, with a greater degree of item-level integration.
5. Greater integration of texts.
6. Broader audiences.
7. Greater range of services.

This deliverable describes the update procedures which are being followed by partners, and outlines the steps in the aggregation pipeline. This was introduced in D5.2 but is repeated here for the sake of completeness. There are two options for aggregation: the standard approach using a suite of tools for the semi-automated aggregation of large data-sets, and a basic approach for the manual upload of small numbers of records. The majority of partners use the standard approach, which has been developed and tested on over one million records from UoY-ADS, from a range of datasets. Aggregation proceeds according to an agreed priority list. ARIADNE subject types are agreed, and partners choose whether they will upload their data via XML files, or automated harvesting methods, such as OAI-PMH.

Partners following the standard approach must:

1. Describe their data according to the AO-Cat using the 3M tool, usually with one mapping per partner;
2. Map subject terms to the Getty AAT using the Vocabulary Matching Tool;
3. Define any period terms used so that they are uploaded to Period0.

Where temporal data needs cleaning to create consistent use of date ranges and periods, partners use an additional tool, Time Spans, to normalise date ranges. They must also ensure that spatial data is compliant with WGS 84.

Partners using FastCat instead manually enter their data records in a spreadsheet-like tool, where the column headings already correspond to AO-Cat core mandatory fields, so that there can be a single mapping covering multiple partners.

Data aggregated by both routes is then transformed into the ARIADNE triplestore, and is also used to create the indices used to power Elasticsearch in the ARIADNE portal. Data is initially loaded into a “staging” portal for checking, before it is published.

Progress is monitored by a software tool, Activity Dash (implemented by FORTH in WP14), which makes it easier to monitor the progress across a large number of partners. An aggregation task force has also met every three weeks on average to review progress and take decisions on next priorities.

Since the initial deliverable D5.2 at M18 we have aggregated an additional 500,000+ data resources, now covering the majority of ARIADNE subject types: archaeological sites and monuments, fieldwork events, fieldwork reports, fieldwork archives, inscriptions, dates, artefacts, rock art, building surveys, maritime, scientific analyses, burial and coins. We have also completed Task 5.1, defining the workflow for new datasets and also the workflow for adding updates to existing datasets, including quarterly updates for fieldwork reports and fieldwork archives from UoY-ADS.

At M18 we had focused on a relatively small number of partners (UoY-ADS, AIAC, HNM, DANS-KNAW, ARUP). This has now been extended to include NIAM-BAS, SND, AU, INFN, ZRC-SAZU, NARA, CONICET and PP, as well as Associate Partner ROCEEH. Work is also at an advanced stage of development for aggregation of data sets from CENIEH, INRAP, OEAW, CNRS, INP, MIBACT-ICU, ASU, LNEC and IAVP, and for Associate Partners at Innsbruck University and the Archaeological Institute of Zagreb. At M36 we have 127 million triples in the public knowledge base and 1.8 million records in the public portal.

The focus for the final 12 months of the project will be to complete the aggregation work and to undertake aggregation from the remaining data provider partners and associate partners.

Since M18 we have also focussed on the development of application profiles for data types which extend the subject range of the ARIADNE infrastructure, and take us into item level aggregation. Some of these were reported in D4.2, and new work, including application profile for excavation data and burials, will be reported in D4.3.

We have also rebuilt the ARIADNE portal so that it reflects the data structure of the new ontology, the AO-Cat, reflecting extensive re-engineering of the Elastic search indices, and adding several enhancements to the portal interface.

Finally, we have started work on the development of VREs which will be built upon the ARIADNEplus data infrastructure, and have provided an ARIADNEplus Lab in D4Science for direct querying of the ARIADNE triplestore. This work will be reported under D12.3 so is simply introduced here.

2 Introduction and Objectives

The deliverable reports the work done in Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.4, 5.5 and 5.7 during the first 36 months of the project, assessing it and planning the related activities for the final period, i.e. months 37-48. Work done under Task 5.6 has previously been reported in D5.1. Related activity has been reported in D4.1 and D4.2.

The overall aim of WP5 is to maintain and extend the ARIADNE Data infrastructure (ADI). This leads to three objectives:

- Keeping the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure up-to-date
- Extending the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure to other sectors
- Keeping the liaisons with other Catalogues, including the future EOSC catalogue of services.

The ARIADNE Data Infrastructure (ADI) was developed during the first ARIADNE infrastructure project, with funding from the European Commission under Framework Programme 7 for the period 2013-2017.¹ ARIADNE's goal was to provide open access to Europe's archaeological heritage and to overcome the fragmentation of digital repositories, placed in different countries and compiled in different languages (Niccolucci and Richards 2019).

Integration has been achieved using state-of-the-art ICT and open data standards, creating the ARIADNE Catalogue with advanced search functionalities and services to use and re-use data.² Innovative vocabulary mapping techniques have brought interoperability to a huge and heterogenous collection of texts, drawings, images, videos, 3D models and maps. ARIADNE succeeded in integrating archaeological datasets in its Registry, with more than 1,700,000 datasets recorded and managed according to the FAIR principles (Aloia et al. 2017).

ARIADNEplus builds upon the success of ARIADNE, extending its scope and improving the technology to embed the ARIADNE infrastructure in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).³ It **extends** ARIADNE in a number of dimensions, covering the domains served and the users addressed:

- The **geographic coverage**, which in ARIADNE already reached almost all European regions, by integrating in the ARIADNEplus Infrastructure a greater number of archaeological partners and giving particular attention to areas where the coverage was less intensive (Figure 1).
- The **disciplinary coverage**, which in ARIADNE included mainly excavation data and a few specialist topics such as, for example, dendrochronology, by integrating in the new ARIADNEplus Infrastructure data produced by palaeoanthropology, bioarchaeology, environmental archaeology as well as the results of scientific analyses, such as material sciences, dating and so on, and those related to standing structures, be they small remains of

¹ <http://legacy.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

² <http://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/>

³ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/>

ancient constructions or complex and massive monuments as, for example, Hadrian's Wall in the UK or the Magna Graecia temples in Southern Italy (Figure 2).

- The **time-span** considered, pushing back the earliest datasets included, by incorporating palaeoanthropology, and forwards the end-date until recent times, e.g. including industrial archaeology and Cold War archaeology; in practice covering the full time-span of the human presence on Earth.
- The **depth of database integration**, exploiting the potential of well-structured datasets such as databases, for which the interoperability will be extended to item level (in ARIADNE implemented only experimentally), and archaeological Geographic Information Systems (GIS), for which integration will be achieved through the introduction of dedicated services, going beyond mere digital maps and overcoming incompatible reference systems.
- The **integration of text datasets** by extending the use of Text Mining through Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Named Entity Recognition (NER), previously applied only experimentally.
- The **research community** involved. The ARIADNEplus target is to make contact with the majority of all researchers and professionals (particularly important in this domain where research and heritage management often go hand in hand), and address most, if not all, of the needs of computer-aware archaeologists. From existing expressions of interest, including the USA, Japan, Latin America and Australia, it is also already anticipated that ARIADNEplus will attract the international research community.
- The **service portfolio** offered to users, incorporating more advanced tools for digital analysis and interpretation in ARIADNEplus.

Figure 1: Extension of geographic coverage from ARIADNE to ARIADNEplus

Figure 2. How ARIADNEplus extends its integration scope in time, space and content

This deliverable reports on progress to date in meeting these objectives.

Section 3 defines the ADI update procedure for both old and new partners. Section 4 discusses the data cleansing procedures. Section 5 describes how the current content of the ADI, inherited from ARIADNE, is being updated and how new data sets are being added, using the AO-Cat (which was described in D4.1). Section 6 discusses enhancements to the AO-Cat since M18 and the addition of VREs to the infrastructure, whilst Section 7 discusses collaboration with related initiatives and cross-discipline interoperability issues with catalogues in other domains, and compatibility with the nascent EOSC catalogue. Finally, Section 8 concludes and summarises priorities for the next phase.

3 Definition of the update procedure of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure. Task 5.1 (NA4.1)

Task leader: UoY-ADS

This task is responsible for defining the most appropriate pipeline for updating the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure, i.e. the pipeline of actions to execute. As previously reported in D5.2, we have adopted an improved ARIADNEplus Data Model (AO-Cat) developed in WP4. This had the consequence that data mappings could be simplified, but all the existing data aggregated during ARIADNE had to be re-processed to reach compliance with AO-Cat (see D4.1).

Therefore, with the agreement that all partners would need to map their data to the AO-Cat from scratch, we have defined a single pipeline for both existing and new data suppliers, although existing Getty AAT and Period0 mappings have been re-used where possible (see Section 4).

Since M18, we have also added a process whereby partners can supply data updates, with a new timestamp, and this can be appended to their existing datasets rather than having to reload these in their entirety. This has been successfully tested with fieldwork reports and fieldwork archives from UoY-ADS.

Aggregation priorities have been defined in Task 4.4 and we have also distinguished between those partners with large data sets who need to undertake a full 3M mapping to the AO-Cat and use the automated tools for aggregation, or those with small datasets which may be manually entered using the Fast Cat tool. These tools were described in D4.1.

A simplified version of the aggregation procedure is shown in Figure 3. In practice, there are also quality control checks at each stage in the pipeline. The D4Science helpdesk is used for partner support, with tickets corresponding to the technical partner supporting each step of the procedure. Experience with the test data has shown that it is an iterative rather than entirely linear process and that stages may need to be repeated before they are completed. For example, the 3M mapping process is a useful mechanism in forcing partners to think about their data in relation to the AO-Cat, and may lead to a need for re-supply of the data.

The aggregation procedure is described in more detail, but in an accessible manner, in the Data Aggregation Pipeline User Guide (Bardi et al. 2020). Since M18, this has been through several updates to reflect changes to the AO-Cat (see Section 6) and it is now in Version 2.2, dated March 2021.

Figure 3: Simplified flowchart showing the update procedure.

During the first phase of ARIADNEplus, the partners in the aggregation task force used a shared GoogleSheet dashboard to define the specific stages and to enter dates as stages were completed. This has now been completely replaced by a new software tool, **Activity Dash**, developed by FORTH as part of T14.1. This has been integrated within D4Science so that all partners can access those tasks for which they have permission, using their existing authentication credentials (Figure 4). The Activity Dash tool tracks several processes (activities) of a workflow, which might or might not be executed in a certain order. It also:

- Provides workflow and activity management,
- Offers a collaborative environment,
- Provides reliable notification means for stakeholders to be updated of any changes on workflow activities they are interested in,
- Is a reference point for stakeholders.

The screenshot shows the Activity Dash interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with icons for home, administration, members, X3ML Mapping Tool, Vocabulary Matching Tool, and Activity Dash. The main content area is titled 'ARIADNEplus - Workflows' and includes a search bar, a 'Show Ongoing Only' toggle, and a 'Select Column Filter' dropdown. The table below lists the workflows with their respective completion percentages.

Name	Description	Completeness	Owner	Avatar
British School of Athens - aggregation of Collection Events database	581 records with information about fieldwork event archives held by BSA	9%	Julian Richards	
LNEC DB-HERITAGE collection	Aggregation DB-HERITAGE buildings database	7.5%	Julian Richards	
INP National Archaeological Database	Aggregation of sites and monuments data for Romania	8%	Julian Richards	
INP Chronicle of Archaeological Research Reports	Aggregation of fieldwork reports for Romania	8%	Julian Richards	
IAVP - Aggregation of Muslim sites and monuments database	Access database of c. 1500 Muslim cemeteries and mosques in eastern Romania; collection record to be provided in FastCat, and data supply via XML file	18%	Julian Richards	
INFN FastCat records	Aggregation of FastCat records from INFN	20%	Julian Richards	
Aggregation of CONICET data from Argentina	Aggregation of 100+ FastCat records for excavations in Argentina	40%	Julian Richards	

Figure 4: Screenshot of the Activity Dash 'dashboard', showing workflows in progress, November 2021. The percentage completed for each workflow is shown in an easily visualised format.

4 Data cleansing. Task 5.2 (NA4.2) Task leader: USW

This task addresses the issue of cleansing the data provided by partners, including mapping of subject terms to the Getty Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT). It also covers the use of Period0 to provide absolute dates for named archaeological periods, as defined by partners, and the Timespan tool to clean period information. The activity is carried out automatically whenever possible, not excluding manual intervention and revision by content providers.

4.1 Subject mapping

The Getty AAT provides identifiers and terms to describe cultural heritage concepts. Getty vocabularies including the AAT are [made available as Linked Open Data](#) (LOD), so each concept in the thesaurus has a unique identifier in the form of a URI (e.g. <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300211545> is the identifier of the concept "penannular brooches"). Continuing with the strategy adopted in the ARIADNE project, ARIADNEplus is using the AAT as a central hub for scalable interconnection of local subject vocabularies. Data providers are required to provide a set of mappings from their own local 'native' subject vocabulary (all terms used to describe subjects in their own metadata) to Getty AAT concepts. The aim is to identify subject mappings from source terms/concepts to concepts that are likely to be useful to assist subsequent browsing and searching of the data, improving recall and precision in search, and to enhance the potential for multilingual interoperability and cross search of the aggregated data records.

4.1.1 Vocabulary Matching Tool

During the first ARIADNE project, a Vocabulary Matching Tool (VMT) was created by USW to assist data providers with creating consistent mappings between their native subject vocabulary concepts and those of the Getty AAT. This tool has been rewritten and improved in the early stages of ARIADNEplus, the new version retaining compatibility with the output format of the first version thus ensuring we could reuse any of the existing mappings already previously created. The [Vocabulary Matching Tool](#) (Figure 5) is a browser-based application with no user installation or configuration requirements, and has been deployed within the ARIADNEplus D4Science web infrastructure. It has a multilingual user interface – at the time of writing the current UI languages supported are German, English, Spanish, French, Italian and Dutch. Users can search and browse the AAT structure, viewing the hierarchical context and scope of each concept to make a far better-informed match than relying on terms alone.

The type of match between the local source concept and the target AAT concept will be one of the possible SKOS mapping properties as defined by the [SKOS reference document](#). There is an associated [online help page](#) with further instructions and general usage guidance to assist users. The tool and its operation are also described in the Data Aggregation Pipeline User Guide document (Bardi et al. 2020).

Vocabulary Matching Tool

English

Source Concept		Match ...	Target Concept		Suggest	Delete Row
Identifier	Label		Filter column...	Filter column...		
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABATTOIR	en	Exact Match	slaughterhouses	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABBEY	en	Exact Match	abbeys (monasteries)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABBOTS SUMMER PALACE	en	Close Match	summer palaces	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ABLUTIONS BLOCK	en	Close Match	rest rooms	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACADEMY SCHOOL	en	Close Match	academies (buildings)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCIDENT HOSPITAL	en	Close Match	hospitals (buildings for health facility)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCOMMODATION BRIDGE	en	Close Match	bridges (built works)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCOMMODATION HUT	en	Close Match	huts (houses)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACCUMULATOR HOUSE	en	Close Match	power plant buildings (utilities buildi...	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACETONE FACTORY	en	Close Match	factories (structures)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACID WORKS	en	Close Match	chemical plants	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ACTIVITY CENTRE	en	Close Match	athletic clubs	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADIT	en	Close Match	mine shafts	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMIRALTY SIGNAL ESTABLISHM...	en	Close Match	signal towers (elevated structures)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMIRALTY SIGNAL STATION	en	Close Match	signal houses	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADMISSION HOSPITAL	en	Close Match	hospitals (buildings for health facility)	Q	⊖
http://purl.org/heritagedata/schemes...	ADULTERINE CASTLE	en	Broad Match	castles (fortifications)	Q	⊖

3979 rows

FIRST PREV 1 2 3 4 5 NEXT LAST

IMPORT JSON
EXPORT JSON
EXPORT CSV
+ ADD NEW ROW
CLEAR ROWS
SHOW HELP

Created by University of South Wales

ARIADNEplus is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission (Grant Agreement No 823914)

This application retrieves some information originating from Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)® which is made available under the ODC Attribution License. See <http://vocab.getty.edu/> for further details.

Figure 5: The Vocabulary Matching Tool, illustrating the ability to define Exact, Close, or Broad matches between the Getty AAT and target concepts in native vocabularies deployed by partners.

4.1.2 AAT mappings created to date

Mappings are inherently reusable as they describe semantic relationships between persistent concepts relating to the domain but are not restricted in scope to a particular dataset. Therefore, in the first instance all 6,400+ existing vocabulary mappings from the preceding ARIADNE project were reused. These were then revised and supplemented as appropriate to account for changes and additions in the interim period; new mappings were also produced by the new ARIADNEplus data providers.

Provider	Description	Mappings
AIAC	(from ARIADNE I) AIAC report that they use Getty AAT terms in their data	129
ARUP	Bilingual – includes mappings for Czech and English terms	2,500
AU	DIME database Danish sites and monuments	425
BUP	Mapping facilities are to be built into their new website	-
CENIEH	CIR	692
CNRS-MASA	PACTOLS to AAT mapping	566
DAI	Books (from ARIADNE I) Collections (from ARIADNE I) Inscription (from ARIADNE I) Monuments (from ARIADNE I) Multi-part monuments (from ARIADNE I) Topographic objects (from ARIADNE I)	17 11 19 176 108 55
DANS-KNAW	DANS-DCCD (from ARIADNE I) DANS-EASY (from ARIADNE I) PAN (PAS equivalent)	336 114 162
FI	tegund hlutverk	221
HNM	MNM-NOK site types. Bilingual mappings	232
IAVP	-	26
INFN	-	6
INRAP	PACTOLS (from ARIADNE I)	1,814
KHM-UO	Artefact terminology (bilingual, English/Norwegian) Find categories (bilingual, English/Norwegian) normertegenstander	1228 136 411

Provider	Description	Mappings
LNEC	LNEC created a bilingual (English/Portuguese) subject vocabulary, mappings are from English terms to AAT concepts	160
MIBAC-ICCU	PICO (from ARIADNE I) ICCU (from ARIADNE I)	144 1,304
NARA	Work ongoing to create a new Japanese controlled vocabulary to be subsequently mapped to Getty AAT	-
NIAM-BAS	(from ARIADNE I) revised and extended	238
OEAW	DFMROE (from ARIADNE I) FH (from ARIADNE I) UK-POOL (from ARIADNE I) UK-THUNAU (from ARIADNE I)	7 10 16 4
PAS-UK	Culture Land use Manufacturing technique Material Surface treatment	7 7 8 28 12
PP	Materials SiteTypes Species AdminRegions SiteNames	54 40 138 13 353
RGK	New data partner, coins data	-
ROCEEH	Interpretation Material Plant remains Category Human remains	13 30 2 18 16
SND	Revised and extended version of previous mappings SHFA – Swedish Rock Art	431 132

Provider	Description	Mappings
UoY-ADS	Building materials (from ARIADNE I) Components (from ARIADNE I) Object types (from ARIADNE I) Maritime craft (from ARIADNE I) Monument types (revised)	12 9 411 24 3,979
Wikidata	Multilingual terms already mapped to AAT (extracted 598,584) Total not included here; see breakdown table below	-
ZRC-SAZU	ARKAS (from ARIADNE I) Supplemented with English term mappings ZBIVA (from ARIADNE I) Supplemented with English term mappings	186 60
	Total:	17,250

Wikidata terms mapped to AAT concepts have been extracted and converted to the same format as output by the Vocabulary Matching Tool. It is envisaged these can be used in the same way as existing native term mappings, to supplement the search vocabulary giving greater potential for multilingual search. The figures are given separately here so as not to be confused with the native vocabulary mappings.

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
ar	Arabic	23,687
bg	Bulgarian	11,446
bs	Bosnian	3,823
cs	Czech	17,946
da	Danish	14,227
de	German	44,111

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
el	Greek	9,265
en	English	55,721
es	Spanish	45,496
fi	Finnish	18,097
fr	French	36,360
ga	Irish	6,212
he	Hebrew	15,646
hr	Croatian	9,051
hu	Hungarian	10,917
is	Icelandic	4,930
it	Italian	25,549
ja	Japanese	27,630
mk	Macedonian	9,693
nl	Dutch	27,259
no	Norwegian	408
pl	Polish	18,919
pt	Portuguese	28,589
ro	Romanian	11,264

Language Code	Language Name	AAT mappings
ru	Russian	28,876
sk	Slovak	8,443
sl	Slovenian	7,635
sq	Albanian	3,479
sr	Serbian	18,980
sv	Swedish	23,601
tr	Turkish	13,299
uk	Ukrainian	18,025
	Total:	598,584

4.2 Period mapping

[Perio.do](http://perio.do) is a multilingual gazetteer of scholarly definitions for describing historical and archaeological named periods. It comprises a series of 'collections' (lists of named periods) where each individual period definition is associated with a particular spatial coverage and a start date and end date, then other metadata including a bibliographic reference for the source of the term. Periods and collections have 'permalink' identifiers (URIs) so they can be clearly and unambiguously referenced - e.g. the identifier <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0rrjd9gix9> defines the period "Moyen Âge" (Middle Ages) within the collection <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0rrjd9> "INRAP: Chronologie Generale. 2007".

Perio.do can accommodate multiple perspectives regarding the dates for a named period for the same spatial extent as shown in the following table, this is why it is important for ARIADNEplus to make explicit the meaning and intended spatial coverage of named periods where they exist in data records.

Identifier	Label(s)	Source	Spatial Coverage	Start	End
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0gigrs6qb2	Bronze Age	Portable Antiquities Scheme	UK	2350 BC	801 BC

Identifier	Label(s)	Source	Spatial Coverage	Start	End
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds7q8m	Bronze Age	Historic England Periods List	UK	2600 BC	700 BC
http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0zj6g8rbvk	Bronze Age	ARENA Portal	UK	2500 BC	700 BC

Named periods are, therefore, defined with reference to periods existing within Perio.do collections. In the first instance, the existing published period collections used in the first ARIADNE project were reused; data partners subsequently created and published additional collections. Period definitions produced by data partners to date are shown in the following table.

Provider (contact)	Description	Periods
AIAC	FASTI - Home. 2004 http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p06v8w4 AIAC report that they use absolute dates in their underlying data	212
ARUP	AMCR Periods Vocabulary http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0wctqt	142
CENIEH	Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, CENIEH. 2021. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0h9ttg	142
DANS-KNAW	Rijksdienst voor het Cultureel Erfgoed. Het Archeologisch Basisregister (ABR). 1992. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0pqptc	53
HNM	No separate Perio.do collection; Hungarian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28 , Hungary)	32
IAMP	Romanian Dobruja Periodisation http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02kbfm	24
INP	Work in progress extracting terms from the 'Treaty of Romanian History'	-
INRAP	INRAP: Institut National de Recherches Archeologiques Preventive. PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data. 2021. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4	123

Provider (contact)	Description	Periods
KHM-UO	Norsk arkeologisk leksikon. 2005. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p04h98g	28
NARA	Agency for Cultural Affairs, Government of Japan. Exhibition of Excavations in the Japanese Archipelago 2020. 2020. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0g8mw8	40
NIAM-BAS	No separate Perio.do collection; Bulgarian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q219 , Bulgaria)	33
OEAW	No separate Perio.do collection; Austrian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q40 , Austria)	31
PAS-UK	Portable Antiquities Scheme. Periods used on the database. 2003. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0gjgrs	31
PP	PP prepared a draft spreadsheet list of cultural periods with Perio.do references.	-
ROCEEH	ROCEEH Out of Africa Database (ROAD) http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0s2rwk	134
SND	No separate Perio.do collection; Swedish periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q34 , Sweden) SHFA (rock Art): Historiska museet. Sök i samlingarna (beta). 2011. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0vn2fr	47 32
UoY-ADS	Heritage Data. Linked Data Vocabularies for Cultural Heritage. 2014. http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds	42
ZRC-SAZU	No separate Perio.do collection; Slovenian periods are included in the aggregated collection "ARIADNE Data Collection. 2015." http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0qhb66 (With spatial coverage http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q215 , Slovenia)	31
	Total:	1,177

4.3 Time Spans Tool

The purpose of using Perio.do in ARIADNEplus is different to the use of AAT mappings - rather than aligning data to common identifiers, Perio.do will be utilized in a subsequent data enrichment stage to enrich records already indexed with named periods (such as “Bronze Age”, “Iron Age” etc.) where the dates associated with these periods are not already made explicit in the input data - determining the intended meaning of named periods in terms of absolute start/end years so that the records can be compared by date and aggregated according to a common timeline. However, in addition to named periods there are occasions where records refer to periods in other forms:

- A span of years (e.g. “1000 BC to 1785 AD”).
- Year with tolerance (e.g. “1666”, “1485+5-10”, “1540±9”)
- A decade (e.g. “the 1920s”)
- Ordinal named or numbered centuries (e.g. “circa C15”, “Early fifteenth century”)
- A span of centuries (e.g. “Late 15th-Mid 17th century”)

Terms of this kind do not exist in Perio.do, and where the start/end years are not easily derived in a consistent way this would prevent these records being compared by date. The terms sometimes have additional prefixes and suffixes (e.g. “circa”, “early”, “AD”, “BCE”). A further complication for the parsing of these strings is multilingual variations in the way they may be expressed.

USW have created a bulk data processing tool to resolve this situation - deriving suitable start/end years from such textual strings. Due to the ARIADNEplus workflow and restriction not to make any changes to the existing records provided by the data provider, it was necessary to make a modified version of the tool functionality to import the ‘raw’ XML data records from the data provider and to supplement any year span values present with new derived start/end year elements, prior to the records being ingested. The example below shows a brief explanatory extract of the output of the tool – a record having an existing “dcterms:temporal” element describing a particular year span has been supplemented with new “minYear” and “maxYear” sibling elements expressing the start/end years as separate xsd:gYear values.

```
<record type="record">
  <dc:title>ST. MARTIN'S CHURCH</dc:title>
  <dc:creator>Exeter City Council</dc:creator>
  <dc:subjectPeriod>
    <dc:subject>CHURCH</dc:subject>
    <dcterms:temporal>850 - 1068</dcterms:temporal>
    <minYear xsi:type="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#gYear">0850</minYear>
    <maxYear xsi:type="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#gYear">1068</maxYear>
  </dc:subjectPeriod>
  . . .
</record>
```

Following initial testing and adjustment the tool was applied to ‘real’ input data using 5 XML files originating from UoY-ADS. The files typically contained a mixture of named periods and year spans. In most cases, named periods were not processed as they would be present in the associated Perio.do collection anyway, so the dates should subsequently be populated through that route. As this was legacy data that did not necessarily conform to the period-based controlled vocabulary currently in

use in the source organization, some special cases were made to accommodate named period terms which, although they did not occur in the associated Perio.do collection, occurred frequently enough to warrant handling e.g. the term *INTER WAR* was considered to mean the period from 1919 to 1938.

The tool takes only a few seconds to process each data file in turn. The results of the bulk data processing work undertaken are shown in the following table:

Input file name	Temporal records	Processed	Not handled
ariadne_324.xml	20,113	18,982	1,131
ariadne_328.xml	59,278	59,278	0
ariadne_1054.xml	971	971	0
ariadne_1970.xml	20,310	20,310	0
ariadne_1972.xml	16,689	16,689	0
Totals	117,361	116,230	1,131

Investigating the “not handled” records (in ADS collection 324) – the majority were for the named period *COLD WAR* – which is actually present in the associated Perio.do collection in any case, so the appropriate dates will subsequently be populated through that route. The remainder (50 records) were using the term *PRE-WORLD WAR I*, which was not considered specific enough to impose an absolute date span.

5 Feeding content into the ARIADNEplus infrastructure. Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 (NA4.3 and NA4.4)

Task leader: CNR-ISTI

This section describes the activities of the Tasks 5.3 (NA4.3 - Updating the current content of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure (ADI)) and 5.4 (NA4.4 - Ingesting data into the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure) led by CNR-ISTI.

The main objectives of the tasks are:

1. Definition of the aggregation workflow
2. Execution of aggregation activities.

5.1 Definition of the aggregation workflow

The previous ARIADNE infrastructure aggregated information about archaeological datasets, described according to the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM). With the adoption of the ARIADNEplus Data Model (AO-Cat) developed in WP4 of the ARIADNEplus project, the data aggregated during the ARIADNE project and already publicly available via the ARIADNE portal must be re-processed to achieve compliance with AO-Cat.

Following the decisions taken in Task 5.1 – Definition of the update procedure of the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure (NA4.1), Task 5.3 has been planned to collect from scratch all the records from the ARIADNEplus partners and transform them according to the AO-Cat model by applying new 3M mappings (defined in the context of Task 4.2 – Mapping dataset metadata to the ARIADNEplus Data Model (NA3.2)).

The complete re-aggregation of content with the new aggregation infrastructure based on the D-Net framework toolkit (developed and operated in WP12) smoothly addresses the two main issues identified in the Description of the Action:

1. Filling the gaps (Sub-task 5.3.1): due to the gap of about two years between ARIADNE and ARIADNEplus, the content available in the ARIADNE infrastructure does not include new and updated records that are available from the data providers.
2. Regular updates (Sub-task 5.3.2): the D-Net framework toolkit natively supports the incremental aggregation of records available via online endpoints (provided incremental collection is supported by the endpoints) and the aggregation workflows can be scheduled to run at given intervals in time. Scheduling is configurable with cron expressions⁴ that can be different for each partner (e.g. DANS data can be aggregated each Monday morning; UoY-ADS data on the 1st of each month). The aggregation schedule is, therefore, agreed with each partner, based on the update frequency of the content on their endpoints.

⁴ Cron expression: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cron#CRON_expression

Thanks to this decision, there was no need to define separate procedures for the aggregation of “old” and “new” content. Therefore, the main objective of both Tasks 5.3 and 5.4 in the first project period was to define the aggregation pipeline (or workflow), i.e. the sequence of steps to be performed for the aggregation of metadata records of the ARIADNEplus partners.

For the definition of the aggregation workflow, an iterative approach has been adopted, where refinements to the different steps have been applied based on requirements, suggestions and feedback from WP4 and WP12. The description of the workflow has been defined in the document “Data Aggregation Pipeline: User Guide” (Bardi et al 2020). The workflow comprises the flows depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6: The aggregation workflow

The flows identified as 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6 in Figure 6 are intended to feed the knowledge base (implemented with an instance of GraphDB⁵):

1. *Ingestion of XML records of the provider.* Records are collected, transformed into AO-Cat by applying a dedicated 3M mapping, and fed into the knowledge base.
2. *Enrichment with Getty AAT subjects⁶.* The subject mapping to Getty AAT (see [Section 4.1](#)) is transformed into RDF by applying the 3M mapping 584 and fed into the knowledge base. As a result, the knowledge base contains the correspondences between native subjects and terms within the Getty AAT vocabulary.
3. *Enrichment with PeriodO.* The PeriodO datasets defined by the provider (see [Section 4.2](#)) are ingested into the knowledge base and used to generate explicit ‘aocat:has_period’ properties.

⁵ GraphDB: <http://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

⁶ Getty AAT: <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/index.html>

4. *Feed the staging knowledge base.* In order to support the providers with checking the content before it is made publicly available, the push on the knowledge base initially targets a “staging” instance. Specific SPARQL INSERT statements are executed (4a) in order to enrich records with AO-Cat properties that are not explicitly available in the mapped records, but that are statically known or can be inferred from other properties or related records (e.g. inheritance of properties of a dataset from its collection). Step 4a also allows the aggregation manager to address possible peculiarities in the data that could complicate the automatic feeding to the portal.
5. *Feed the staging A+ portal.* For each set of records ingested via step 1, a procedure reads the corresponding triples and builds json records to feed the index server that serves the A+ portal. The procedure will include in the json records the properties that have been added by the other steps (2-3) and others that can be inferred exploiting the reasoning capability of GraphDB. Initially, the goal of this flow was to generate records that could be used by the previous ARIADNE portal. The procedure has been updated to include properties that were not available in ACDM but that have been added in the AO-Cat and are useful to the new ARIADNEplus portal for the implementation of advanced discovery functionality.
6. *Feed the public knowledge base.* This flow is executed if the provider successfully completed the content checking on the staging knowledge base and portal.
7. *Feed the public A+ portal.* The flow applies the same procedure as step 5, using the public instances of the knowledge base and portal instead of the staging instances.

Steps 4 and 5 supports the quality checks of content and will be bypassed once the input format of the records and the 3M mappings of a provider are stable, so that it will be possible to automatically update the knowledge graph and the ARIADNEplus portal with updated and new records without human intervention. If necessary, steps 4 and 5 might be reactivated for a given source (e.g. because the provider upgraded the information system and wants to perform extensive checks before the data supplied by the new system goes public).

5.2 Execution of aggregation activities

The aggregation activities have been planned to support the work and match the timeline of WP12 (for the development and deployment of the services of the aggregative infrastructure and new versions of the portal) and WP4 (for the preparation of 3M mappings).

Phase 1: testing the aggregative infrastructure with UoY-ADS records

The content update on the new A+ infrastructure has been tested with records provided by the ADS. This phase informed WP12 about requirements and needed to be fulfilled with the integration of additional tools and services for data processing and curation that were not foreseen in the DoA. This phase was completed in June 2020.

Phase 2: aggregation of records of ARIADNE partners according to the pipeline defined in T5.1

This phase started at the end of June 2020 and by December 2021 resulted in the aggregation of 17 providers (five of them still at the staging phase, as detailed in the tables below), for a total of 127

million triples in the public knowledge base and 1.8 million records in the public portal, and for a total of 132 million triples in the staging knowledge base, 10,000 records in the staging portal.

Aggregation details by partner/source is shown in the tables below, including both records per partner/dataset on the public portal, and records per partner/dataset on the staging portal. Most of the data sets have been re-aggregated and re-published on the portals several times due to one or more of the following reasons:

- Updates to the AO-Cat ontology
- Updates to the portals
- Fine tuning of the mappings
- Improvements to the enrichment step
- Updated input data from the provider
- Changes to the provider's endpoint.

Aggregated records available in the public portal as of December 2021

Provider	# records in public portal (approx)
ADS	1.4M
AIS CR	230K
HNM	60K
DANS	50K
Swedish Rock Art	25K
International Association for Classical Archaeology	14K
Aarhus University (DIME)	8.6K
ZRC SAZU	8.3K
Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities	6.6K
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	945
SND	500
University of Patras	3

Aggregated records available on the staging portal as of December 2021

Provider	# records in staging portal (approx)
CENIEH	705
INFN	20
IDACOR (CONICET/UNC)	2
Swedish National Data Service	1
NARA	1

6 Extending the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure scope. Task 5.5 (NA4.5) Task leader: CNR-ISTI

In the first 18 months of the project, the Consortium members in charge of Task T5.5 focussed on endowing the ARIADNE Catalogue ontology (AO-Cat, as it is named within the Consortium) with the vocabulary needed to model people, institutions and services at the Catalogue level. The vocabulary includes classes, properties and the axioms providing the meaning of these in relation with the other classes and properties of the AO-Cat. A full account of AO-Cat was given in Deliverable D4.1 (Initial report on dataset integration), so this section will focus on enhancements to AO-Cat since M18 and initial steps to develop Virtual Research Environments (VREs) based on the ARIADNE Data Infrastructure.

In addition to the usual adjustments that always accompany the development of a knowledge base such as the ARIADNE Content Cloud (simply “AC” hereafter), there have been two major additions:

- representation of uncertainty in spatial regions, and
- representation of digital images associated with archaeological records collected and integrated by the project.

Each addition is described in a separate subsection below. The last subsection of this section introduces the initial steps taken by the Consortium to develop VREs based on the ARIADNE Data Infrastructure, although these are more fully reported in D12.3.

6.1 Representing uncertainty in spatial regions

Some data providers have asked to accompany the information about the spatial region covered by a data resource with a further specification of precision. This may be due to several reasons, such as:

- The data provider has sensitive spatial data which they do not wish to make publicly available, maybe to protect the precise location of a site. Therefore, they should only supply to ARIADNE the data at a resolution which they are willing to make publicly available. *e.g.* for the UK Portable Antiquities Scheme this is the parish administrative unit, and we would then use Geonames to provide a centroid point for the parish.
- The data provider may only hold data for site location at an imprecise level, so we need to make it clear when we plot locations on a map, that the point represents the site location to the nearest 10km, for example.

In order to deal with these and similar cases, we have added the property ‘has_spatial_precision’ associating a data resource with a specification of the precision that characterizes the spatial coverage of the resource. Note that a resource may cover at most one spatial region, therefore, such precision specification can always unambiguously be referred to the appropriate region.

As to the range of property ‘has_spatial_precision’, we observe that some providers are able to say exactly how accurate the points they supply are, while others are only able to give a qualitative

assessment. On balance, it has been decided to allow providers to give a quantitative specification, for three reasons:

1. Whenever that information is available, the AO-Cat makes it possible to represent it.
2. A quantitative specification will be very useful when displaying the points on a map.
3. A quantitative specification will avoid creating a special vocabulary for a qualitative specification, such as “high”, “medium”, “low”.

For the specification of quantitative information, we have, therefore, introduced class ‘AO_Dimension’, a subclass of ‘crm:E54 Dimension’, as the range of property ‘has_spatial_dimension’. There are two properties that have ‘AO_Dimension’ as domain:

- ‘has_value’, sub-property of ‘crm:P90 has value’, for associating a numeric value with the specification, ‘range is rdfs:Literal’
- ‘has_unit’, sub-property of ‘P91 has unit’, for associating a unit of measurement with the specification, ‘range is AO_Concept’.

In addition to these properties, property ‘has_type’, already part of AO-Cat, can be used for associating a type with the specification.

6.2 Representing digital images

During the first 18 months of the project, the following requirements concerning digital images have emerged:

- To display one or more images (thumbnails, in fact) along with the data about a resource on the Portal. Any kind of resource can have associated thumbnails. In particular:
 - an individual data resource can have thumbnails portraying the resource it is about (i.e. the obverse and reverse of a coin)
 - a collection data resource can have thumbnails relative to any subset of the items it contains
 - the thumbnails associated with a service can be, for instance, the logo of the service.
- Amongst the provided thumbnails, providers would like to have the possibility of indicating a primary image, to be used wherever a single image needs to be selected for the record (for instance, in a search result).
- The displayed thumbnails must be web resources on the provider’s site, i.e. they must be identified by a local URI and accessible through that URI on the provider’s site.
- Providers are given the option of copying the thumbnails to be displayed into the AC (for a fixed maximum size), or keeping these thumbnails exclusively in their own storage, to be accessed at display time by the Portal software. The latter solution will be encouraged by the ARIADNE guidelines, to avoid the problem of storing too many images in the AC, and the consequent copyright or update problems.
- Each thumbnail copied into the AC is given a URI on the ARIADNE namespace; that URI must be associated with the link to the original thumbnail on the provider’s site for reference.
- Each thumbnail copied into the AC must be licensed under licence CC0 by the provider.

In Figure 7:

- classes are in light blue, while arcs are labelled by the property corresponding to their colours, given in the bottom part of the figure
- ai:idr_106900 is an individual data resource, namely a record provided by the project DIME for sharing through the ARIADNE infrastructure. In the AC, this resource:
 - refers to the coin ai:coin_106900, an instance of AO_Object
 - has the digital images ai:di_1 to ai:di_4 as visual components; these images are the same as the DIME resources dime_1 to dime_4, respectively.
- the actual images are obtained via dereferencing of the corresponding URIs by the appropriate web server, either on the ARIADNE infrastructure (for the URIs of the form ai:di_n) or on the DIME project site (for the URIs of the form dime_n).

Whenever the record is modified on the DIME site, for instance by replacing one or more of the four images (dime_i) by different images identified by different URIs, that record must be re-aggregated. The same must be done if any one of the four images is modified on the DIME site but the URIs that identify the modified images remain the same, because the image associated with the URI is copied into the AC.

For generality, the model does not make any assumption about the relationships between the images that are part of the record (ai:di_1 to ai:di_4 in the example) and the object (ai:coin_106900) that the record refers to. If desired, such relationships can be asserted as additional information. In the above example, in CRM terms any one of the four images that are the content of the digital images ai:di_j is a visual representation of the coin; this can be asserted by using property P138 represents between the coin and the content of each digital image. Such level of detail is not necessary to capture the requirements stated above, therefore the classes and properties for representing this information are not part of the present model.

Figure 8 illustrates the model for images that are not copied into the AC. For illustrative purposes the same object as the one used in Figure 7 is used, assuming the corresponding thumbnails are not copied into the AC:

The main difference from the previous diagram is that the four images are not part of the AC, they are just referred to in statements, where they are identified using the URIs of the providers.

6.3 VRE development: initial steps

Planning has also continued for the development of Virtual Research Environments (VRE) within the ARIADNEplus D4Science infrastructure. Two VRE use case workshops were held online in 2021 (see D2.3 Section 5), and two more are planned for 2022. In addition, CNR have created an ARIADNEplus Lab which gives researchers access to a number of online tools with which they can directly interact with the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base:

- (1) The JupyterHub enables the exploitation of computational environments and resources without burdening users with installation and maintenance tasks. The JupyterHub environment is *(i)* preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and *(ii)* provides access to the Workspace enabling sharing of resources with other members much easier.
- (2) GraphDB provides researchers with access to the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base, including all the partner data as a Linked Open Data set and modelled according to the ARIADNE ontology. With GraphDB, researchers can explore the knowledge base with the available web GUI or programmatically with SPARQL queries.
- (3) The DataMiner Analytics Engine permits the execution of an array of analytics methods by transparently relying on distributed computing infrastructure. Executions can run either on multi-core machines or on different computational platforms, such as D4Science and other different private and commercial Cloud providers. New software can be integrated by using a dedicated Software Importer (SAI).
- (4) RStudio provides an integrated development environment for the R programming language. It includes a console and a syntax-highlighting editor and it enables code execution. Tools for plotting are also included. The RStudio environment is *(i)* preconfigured with libraries and packages to ease the execution of common data analytics tasks, and *(ii)* provides seamless access to the ARIADNEplus Workspace enabling sharing of resources with other members much easier.

The development of these VREs is more fully described in D12.3.

7 Collaborating with other Catalogues. Task 5.7 (NA4.7) Task leader: PIN

This task is responsible for collaborating and addressing cross-discipline interoperability issues with catalogues in other domains, as well as for ensuring compatibility with the future EOSC catalogue, and with OpenAIRE. It also involves partnerships with other archaeological aggregators, developed as part of WP2, including Pelagios, ROCEEH, and THANADOS.

7.1 Collaboration with generic platforms and initiatives

The development of the TEXTCROWD framework has also continued since M18. Originating in the Science Demonstrators of the EOSCpilot⁷ initiative (where the ARIADNE community was represented by PIN, supported by CNR) the TEXTCROWD system was released at the end of the project as a public service in the D4Science cloud environment provided by CNR-ISTI⁸. The EOSCpilot duration overlapped with ARIADNEplus only for a short period. However, it was possible to demonstrate the needs and solutions of the archaeological community in the EOSC framework.

The tool has been entirely re-engineered in ARIADNEplus and now uses Supervised Machine Learning algorithms (Conditional Random Fields and Neural Networks) to learn an entity recognition model from examples of documents annotated by experts. Its state-of-the-art Named Entity Recognition (NER) engine is now capable of efficiently processing streams with large amounts of documents and detect entities of various types, such as institutions, people, events, places, objects, periods and dates, in archaeological reports, excavation diaries and other similar textual documents. During the last period, TEXTCROWD has been trained with a set of about 200 manually annotated archaeological documents in Italian and this resulted in the definition of more precise recognition functions and a noticeable improvement in performance.

For the annotation of archaeological documents, we chose to use the INCEpTION⁹ framework. INCEpTION is an open-source set of tools capable of interfacing with TEXTCROWD in order to provide bidirectional functionalities, acting, on the one hand, as a suggester for manual annotations and providing, on the other hand, a self-training facility for the TEXTCROWD's machine learning engine based on the human annotations. An integrated system including TEXTCROWD and INCEpTION is being defined and will soon be released as a full annotation and text mining service in one of the forthcoming ARIADNEplus VREs.

In the framework of the collaboration between ARIADNEplus and EOSC-Pillar¹⁰, INFN and PIN have developed a cloud system, called THESPIAN (Tools for HERitage Science Processing, Integration, and

⁷ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu>

⁸ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd>

⁹ <https://inception-project.github.io>

¹⁰ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu>

ANalysis), intended to offer multiple microservices to the researchers of the Cultural Heritage Network (CHNet) of INFN (Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare) and to the ARIADNEplus infrastructure, including the storage of raw data and their reuse according to the FAIR principles for establishing integration and interoperability among shared information.

The THESPIAN system is currently composed of two integrated web services: THESPIAN-Mask, a service for assisted metadata generation and data storage, based on the CRMhs ontology and THESPIAN-NER, a tool based on a deep neural network for Named Entity Recognition, capable of interpreting Italian-written scientific documents and annotating them, extracting named entities that can be used for devising custom database queries inside the system.

The main goal of THESPIAN-Mask is to offer a cloud environment for the storage of metadata related to scientific information (including analysis procedures and protocols, scientific reports etc.) together with their raw data, processed data, results and documentation, article preprints and so forth. CRMhs is the ontology on which the application profile for scientific data developed by ARIADNEplus for item level integration is based. This allows the THESPIAN system to export semantic information which is already compatible with the ARIADNEplus data framework.

THESPIAN-NER is a Natural Language Processing (NLP) tool for automatic Named Entity Recognition (NER) of scientific entities using deep learning techniques (namely a Convolutional Neural Network). It was built using the spaCy Python library¹¹ and has been trained using Italian scientific reports and other textual documents provided by the CHNet research network. The tool extends TEXTCROWD as it was included as one of Tasks of the current EOSC-Pillar project, and has the goal of linking data from heritage science with archaeological information produced in other environments, such as ARIADNEplus. It allows users to automatically annotate scientific documents written in Italian (either .txt or .pdf files) by identifying and labelling relevant semantic scientific entities in the text, extract and use them to define new metadata for the annotated documents in order to classify them in an automatic way. The extracted entities can be also exported and integrated in other semantic environments, and used for building custom queries to fetch related records available on the THESPIAN-MASK data cloud. Future developments include plans to “export” the same approach to France and the French language; for this, the reference EOSC-Pillar partner is CNRS, also an ARIADNEplus partner.

THESPIAN-NER is available for researchers as a web tool hosted by the CHNet server in the CHNet cloud environment¹². Since it enables researchers to annotate locally stored as well as remotely available documents provided by the CHNet servers through the cloud platform, it constitutes a (micro)service aiming at fostering data (re)usability.

In addition to the aforementioned services, designed to be fully compatible and to establish interaction among the two ecosystems, ARIADNEplus has worked to make its platform fully

¹¹ <https://spacy.io>

¹² <https://chnet-000.fi.infn.it>

interoperable with the EOSC cloud by means of the D4Science platform, used to implement the Virtual Research Environments in which the ARIADNEplus cloud services operate. D4Science is now largely compatible and interoperable with EOSC at cloud level, and already shares some services and features with it, including authentication and management of federated identities, interconnection of distributed infrastructures, and orchestration of distributed services.

PIN, together with CNR and INFN, are strongly involved in the global development of EOSC and are constantly keeping ARIADNEplus partners informed about the progress of all these activities. In addition, UoY-ADS, DANS-KNAW and CNR are also partners in SSHOC, where UoY-ADS represents the Heritage Science community and is responsible for a deliverable addressing the challenges of FAIR data in the heritage science and archaeological communities. This also ensures useful cross-fertilisation between ARIADNEplus and EOSC.

Finally, ARIADNEplus work on digital libraries has been undertaken in collaboration with OpenAIRE, which is one of the services now integrated with EOSC¹³. The OpenAIRE Community Gateway for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage offers a view of the OpenAIRE Research Graph¹⁴ including literature, datasets, software, other research products, and projects; all linked to each other relative to the domain of Digital Humanities. This broad definition includes Humanities, Cultural Heritage, History, Archaeology, and related fields. Users can discover scientific outputs and browse their discipline-specific graph, monitor Open Science statistics over time, and by accessing Zenodo¹⁵ also deposit/publish new products by assigning them to this community. This gateway offers a single-entry point for discovering research products relevant in the domain of Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage available in the OpenAIRE Research Graph.

OpenAIRE's mission is closely linked to the mission of the European Commission: to provide unlimited, barrier free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. OpenAIRE fulfils the EOSC vision substantially, as its operations already provide the glue for many of the user and research driven functionalities, including domain disciplined research communities or Research Infrastructures. In particular, the OpenAIRE Research Graph is one of the authoritative sources for the European Open Science Cloud. With this collaboration with OpenAIRE, ARIADNEplus is thus ensuring compatibility with the future EOSC catalogue, which is one of the key objectives of Task T5.7.

7.2 Collaboration with other archaeological and anthropological aggregators

Contacts with Pelagios have also continued in this period. Pelagios is a network which includes North American partners and covers the classical world (see D2.2)¹⁶ and developed tools such as Recogito¹⁷, an annotation framework that allows the creation of relationships between textual fragments or areas

¹³ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/digital-humanities-and-cultural-heritage-openaire-community-gateway>

¹⁴ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org>

¹⁶ <https://pelagios.org>

¹⁷ <https://recogito.pelagios.org>

of images, and geographical entities in order to define geographic maps of textual and semantic content. The ongoing collaboration with Pelagios includes the definition of a series of case studies spanning various disciplines, in which archaeology, cultural and digital heritage interact and become interoperable both at the level of data and as regards tools and services. The interaction of the services developed by ARIADNEplus with the tools provided by Pelagios aims to create a distributed digital platform, based on the Linked Open Data paradigm, capable of providing answers to complex, interdisciplinary scientific questions by querying a network of interlinked information. The analysis of how to implement a complex interaction of this type is still ongoing and will be made fully operational in the next period.

During the previous reporting period, ARIADNEplus established a close collaboration with the ROCEEH project for the acquisition and integration of their archives, and collaborating in developing a long-term preservation strategy for their paleoanthropological data. Since 2008 the project "The Role of Culture in Early Expansions of Humans" (ROCEEH) of the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences and Humanities¹⁸ has gathered c.8,000 archaeological assemblages from c.1,700 localities in Africa/Eurasia, stored in the ROAD database, which has a limited public access page¹⁹. The data comprise predominantly early human cultural and biological artifacts, as well as environmental data, which have been excerpted from scientific publications and their own excavations (e.g. UNESCO Swabian Jura).

In order to provide access to ROAD via ARIADNEplus, its data schema has been mapped to AO-Cat using the 3M tool; the ROAD vocabularies have been mapped to Getty AAT and the cultural terminology (Arch-Strat) has been uploaded and made available through the Perio.dO system. As a result of these activities, carried out in close collaboration between ROCEEH and ARIADNEplus, almost 7,000 paleoanthropology records have been published on the ARIADNEplus portal.

ARIADNEplus has also begun a collaboration with the THANADOS project²⁰ (The Anthropological and Archaeological Database of Sepultures), an aggregator for information about burials hosted at the Natural History Museum of Vienna, funded by the Austrian Academy of Sciences, the Austrian Archaeological Institute, MEDCEM²¹ (Medieval Cemeteries at the Periphery of the Carolingian World) based at the Archaeological Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences, the European Union and the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic.

THANADOS has now joined ARIADNEplus as an Associate Partner with the aim of integrating the THANADOS data into the AC. The THANADOS data concerns burials (see Figure 9), so in terms of the ARIADNE conceptual framework, they are item-level data that fit under an Application Profile. The definition of the mappings for periods and subjects have already been established and we are in the process of aggregating their data in the ARIADNEplus Catalogue. A series of meetings and interactions with THANADOS experts have already been held and will continue in the next period to complete this

¹⁸ <http://www.roceeh.net/home/>

¹⁹ http://www.roceeh.uni-tuebingen.de/roadweb/smarty_road_simple_search.php

²⁰ <https://thanados.net>

²¹ <https://medcem.aiscr.cz>

process. As a prerequisite, the ARIADNEplus Consortium is developing the Burials Application Profile that should accommodate the THANADOS data, as well as other burials data present in the ARIADNE Consortium, into the AC. Technically, the Application Profile will be fully compatible with the CIDOC CRM, with the possible addition of classes and properties coming from a CRM extension, such as CRMArcheo and CRMSci.

Figure 9: The THANADOS top-level data model

Once the Application Profile has been developed, mappings from the THANADOS data to the profile will be defined, following the consolidated aggregation approach of the project. These mappings are going to transform the four-level hierarchies (cemetery - graves - stratigraphic units - finds) in which the THANADOS data are organized, into RDF graphs compliant with the AO-Cat ontology and with the Application Profile.

Once the mappings are completed, the ARIADNE aggregation team will collect the data from the THANADOS server and apply the mappings to them. This step will rely on a special purpose API that the THANADOS project is developing to serve their data in a suitable XML format.

8 Conclusions

In conclusion, we have made significant progress in improving the procedures for updating and extending the ARIADNEplus infrastructure from those which were used during the first ARIADNE project. The development and testing of these tools occupied much of our first year, in order to ensure they are fit for purpose, but we now have a clear pipeline, and are making excellent progress in aggregating partner datasets. Since M18, we have begun to extend the infrastructure to accommodate new ARIADNE subject types, demonstrating the powerful benefits for researchers in being able to cross-search multiple datasets, of different data types, from different data providers. By M36 we have 127 million triples in the public knowledge base and 1.8 million records in the public portal. We have also begun work on item level integration, continued work on the development of Application Profiles for specific subdomains, and commenced the introduction of VREs, including an ARIADNEplus Lab which gives researchers access to a suite of tools which allow them to interrogate the ARIADNEplus Knowledge Base. The implementation of VREs will be completed in the final 12 months, supporting the case studies planned under WP16.

A notable highlight has been the number of other archaeological and anthropological data aggregators that have approached us to incorporate access to their data in the ARIADNE portal. This has already been accomplished for the ROCEEH early human origins group, and work is now well underway on adding data from the Austrian-based burials aggregator, THANADOS.

This work will be continued and concluded during the final 12 months of the project, ensuring full coverage of all ARIADNEplus partners, as well as the growing number of Associate Partners who wish to use our services to make their data available beyond their national borders, including Innsbruck University and the Archaeological Institute of Zagreb. We will extend the experiments undertaken on item level integration in ARIADNE, and use the power of the CIDOC CRM (and the fact that the AO-Cat is fully compliant with it) to demonstrate interoperability and connections between dataset at a variety of scales, and with complex relations with other data types. We will also extend current activity in order to catalogue services, and we will work to ensure that the ARIADNE Data Infrastructure is able to take its place within EOSC and the wider network of infrastructure providers.

9 References

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